

TalX Workshop 1: Practitioner Perspectives on Well-Adapting Places

Date: March 29th & 30th 2021

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Introduction

Global climate is changing and the impacts of these changes pose significant risks to society, the economy and the environment, however, early proactive adaptation can not only lessen these risks but also deliver benefits. Adaptation is a new area of planning and there is an urgent requirement to increase the capabilities of local and sectoral decision makers to plan, implement and manage ‘on the ground’ adaptation through existing policies (i.e. mainstreaming). On the basis of international best practice and the experiences of adaptation planning, this EPA-funded Transboundary Adaptation Learning Exchange (TalX) project will provide a learning and collaborative space to exchange experiences of adaptation, provide for transboundary learning opportunities and increase the decision making capacity for adaptation across the UK and Ireland. The five jurisdictions (Republic of Ireland, Northern Ireland, Scotland, Wales and England) that form the focus of the research are subject to similar climate risks, have similar structures of governance, but are at different stages of maturity in adaptation planning and implementation. This provides an opportunity to support a cross-jurisdictional learning network, that will enable and support the development and acceleration of climate adaptation action.

In order to develop this learning network and enable effective climate adaptation the TalX project has three main objectives:

1. Identify best practice criteria for climate adaptation planning and assess the enabling environment for climate adaptation across the five case study jurisdictions (Ireland, Northern Ireland, Scotland, Wales and England);
2. Identify the key dimensions for effective adaptation and create a capability maturity model (CMM) that supports cross-jurisdictional learning and to enable the implementation of good climate adaptation practises;
3. Establish a learning network across the case study jurisdictions to accelerate progress and allow for the monitoring and evaluation of the CMM in different contexts.

To support the development of the learning network and to ensure progress in developing effective adaptation, a place-based adaptation capability and maturity model is being developed as part of TalX activities. A maturity model provides a framework composed of structured levels that aims to improve existing processes within an organisation/business/department. Each maturity level represents a specific stage of development and provides a foundation of practises and attributes on which subsequent levels can be built.

The TalX project will work with adaptation practitioners to co-create a CMM to support the development of adaptation capabilities in the 5 jurisdictions. The CMM will be developed to support place-based adaptation and at a scale where a sense of place and the ability to influence change co-exist (i.e., an administrative area with established governance structures, decision-making processes, democratic participation and the influence and ability to administer and deliver policy and finance instruments). The CMM will provide a framework that supports the combination of top-down and bottom-up adaptation actions and allow for the mainstreaming and acceleration of climate adaptation. It aims to benefit all stakeholders acting in the ‘place’, including public sector organisations, local government, communities and businesses, by developing and progressing the capabilities necessary to enable well adapting places.

The first TalX workshop aimed to establish the key adaptation concepts of what a well-adapted place is and the activities and capabilities necessary to achieve this. The workshop was targeted at expert climate adaptation practitioners and policymakers from across the 5 jurisdictions (Appendix 1).

Workshop Structure

To support workshop activities and prior to the workshop, a [pre-recorded video](#) was circulated to all participants providing an overview of the TalX project. The workshop was delivered online and over two days with 2 hours on each day. Each day was comprised of two work sessions (WS).

- Day 1 (March 29th, 2021) focused on determining the key characteristics of good place-based adaptation (WS 1) and the capabilities required to achieve good place-based adaptation (WS 2);
- Day 2 (March 30th, 2021) refined and grouped the capabilities identified for good place-based adaptation (WS3) and discussed how adaptation capabilities can be developed to support the delivery of 'good' place -based adaptation over time (WS4).

WS1 introduced participants to the TalX project and identified their perspectives of what a well-adapting place was. This consisted of a presentation followed by a breakout discussion and a discussion in plenary. The presentation provided an overview of the TalX project, including the work so far and the future steps for the project. WS2 encouraged participants to think about what activities they have done to help them on their journey towards a well adapting place and consisted of 2 breakout discussions.

Between WS2 and WS3 the project group clustered the activities and capabilities identified in WS2. These groupings were then presented to the workshop participants during WS3, and the identified capabilities of a well-adapting place were adjusted, refined and prioritised during a breakout discussion and a discussion in plenary. WS4 was a maturity mapping exercise to discuss how the prioritised capabilities evolve over time and consisted of a breakout discussion and a discussion in plenary.

Results

The work sessions were coordinated via Miro, where the outputs of the working sessions are stored. They are available at: [TalX Workshop March 29-30th, Online Whiteboard for Visual Collaboration \(miro.com\)](#). The results are summarised for each of the work sessions below.

Work Session 1 (Table 1) highlighted that the participants considered a well-adapted place to have particular attributes or characteristics that have been grouped thematically. The key themes identified included: mainstreaming and a holistic approach; sustainability; knowledge/research; community engagement, communication, collaboration and education; policy, decision-making and planning; action; justice; resilience; nature-based solutions and green/blue infrastructure; visioning; resources/funding; leadership/champions and recognition of emotion.

Work Session 2 (Tables 2 & 3) identified the actions that participants had taken on their journey towards shaping a well adapting place and the capabilities necessary to do this. In terms of activities, there were several key themes that the participants felt had helped them enable climate adaptation (Table 2), these activities have been classified as those activities relating to Education, Knowledge, Research and Learning; Policy, Decision-making and Planning; Monitoring, Evaluation and Accountability; Leadership/Champions and Co-ordination; Visioning, and Action. However, the main areas of action that appear to have supported adaptation were: Community Engagement, Communication and Collaboration; and the presence of appropriate Resources and Funding.

The key capabilities identified (Table 3) as being required to support action included the development and implementation of effective legislative or policy drivers, this was considered essential by all groups, with many raising the point that some stakeholders tend to focus on activities only within their remit and if there is no onus on them to include adaptation it won't be developed. The ability to effectively communicate and engage with communities, especially in identifying how climate adaptation will benefit them, not just from an environmental perspective but also economically and socially (place-making) was another key capability identified. The ability to develop a clear and compelling vision of the type of future each place/community wanted was also an important capability. The ability to access and employ resource, funding and capacity building was considered a key capability to support sustained momentum and on the ground action, and implementation (even at small-scale) was also identified as necessary to hold public engagement and enthusiasm. There was a good deal of overlap in WS1 and WS2, with many of the attributes that the participants viewed as an aspect of a well-adapting place also identified as an activity or capability needed to create a well-adapting place (eg., leadership skills).

Work Session 3 (Table 4) involved clustering and prioritising the adaptation capabilities identified in WS2. This grouping was first done by the project team and then refined by the workshop participants. WS3 identified thirteen core themes for enabling adaptation, these were then prioritised by the participants into the top 6 essential capabilities necessary to create a well-adapting place. The prioritised capabilities included: the ability to effectively engage, communicate and work with communities; the ability to collaborate with different networks and partners; the ability to provide good leadership and to take ownership of decisions and actions; the ability to develop and implement effective legislation or policy drivers; the ability to obtain/access sustained and secure funding and resource; and the ability to access and employ research, knowledge and expertise effectively.

Work Session 4 (Table 5) involved a maturity mapping exercise and discussed how the 6 prioritised capabilities identified in WS3 evolve over time. Each group discussed 2 of these prioritised

capabilities and what they would look like in a place beginning their adaptation journey right through to a mature well-adapted place. An example of 2 of these capabilities at different maturity stages are shown below:

The ability to develop and implement effective legislation or policy drivers:

- Less mature – This is where adaptation is more of a tick-box exercise to meet the minimum requirements with only a basic level of voluntary in-house reporting on progress
- Medium maturity – At this stage there is regulation and not just policy, with some level of strategic coherence between policies. There is also action towards knowledge ad capacity building and mechanisms in place to support this
- More mature – At this point there is mandatory legislation with alignment between policies and explicit outcomes to maximize the benefits across all sectors. There is independent regulation of adaptation that is integrated into the existing structures and published results. Adaptation actions are constitutional and not subject to the whims of the government of the day.

The ability to collaborate with different networks and partners:

- Less mature – At this stage there is a lack of knowledge of the key contacts (where/with whom the knowledge and expertise reside) necessary for action. Adaptation is being carried out by multiple people alongside their other responsibilities rather than as a dedicated role and diverse views and opinions are focused on their own narrow considerations rather than all adaptation actions.
- Medium maturity - At this stage the entity's structure and aims are well defined and there is a clear stipulation of what is expected within each role in terms of engagement and input from all partners. The actors involved in adaptation are well-known and involved and stakeholders and leaders know the contact points.
- More mature - At this point there is sustained involvement from the lead coordinator, with recognition that partners come and go on projects and that they must be flexible enough to adapt. Collaboration has become the norm, with projects liaising with a wide range of different partners and networks and monitoring that provides legitimacy and transparency in order to measure success for all involved parties.

Table 1: Summary of WS1 results: What do you envision when you picture a well-adapted place?

Theme	Identified Attributes
Mainstreaming & Holistic Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Adaptation, mitigation & biodiversity are equal and not competing and a holistic approach considering wider benefits is used • Adaptation is mainstreamed across all areas of planning (including spatial planning), environment and society and in all decision making • Acceptance of shared responsibilities both public & private (adaptation is not just the job of environmental officers) • Realising the cross cutting nature of climate adaptation - with linkages across organisations / activities routinely happen • Considering interacting risks and unintended consequences (maladaptation) - and multiple benefits
Sustainability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Considering the intended lifetime of the initiative and regulatory requirements • Principles of sustainability being applied to place-based adaptation – e.g., Welsh Future Generations Act • Benefiting biodiversity • Sustainable use of resources • Green economy and maximizing co-benefits first (such as job creation)
Knowledge/Research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Science based targets and evidence based informed adaptation actions • Acceptance of the uncertainties and acknowledgement of a pathway approach to adaptation • Places have a genuine, spatial climate change risk and vulnerability assessment and it is reviewed regularly and underpins other plans • An educated society at all levels (from household to national) • An evidence base around climate risks, (preferably spatial) that is transparent and accessible to all • Knowledge of risk is translated to the operational level • Considering design options where co-benefits are realised • Realising opportunities for learning, review, course correction, and for ongoing improvement of strategies and plans • Clear indications of what change is needed at a strategic level to support adaptation and of the sufficiency of current plans and any major gaps • Knowledge of which decisions need high levels of adaptive capacity and which don't - i.e. where you need to prioritise resources
Community Engagement, Communication, Collaboration and Education	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Locally developed and managed solutions used in plan development which adopt the principles of co-design (authentic collaboration - not just tick box consultations) • Open conversations about acceptable losses, who/what wins and who loses and acceptance by stakeholders that some assets/ elements/ communities will be lost and cannot be protected completely • Opportunities for different parts of the community to connect , collaborate, make decisions together- 'facilitating mechanisms' • Strong focus on community and adult education • Effective communication strategy • Encouraging place based innovation and empowerment • More democratized and effective forms of governance
Policy, Decision-Making and Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate risks being a key criterion across all decision making and planning development • Recognising and planning for a worst-case scenario (4-degree world) • Clear line of sight from strategy/policy to local priorities and action • Policy meeting national and local needs and priorities • Accountability for decision making and delivering actions which emerge is prioritised • Adaptation is supported by a strong policy framework

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategic coherence across policies and programs • Long term awareness is included in decision-making • A step change in policy thinking around industrial strategy, transport, planning, etc and a more restricted and limited agricultural sector
Action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demonstrating evidence of moving beyond tinkering and modest sideways reforms - with specific actions for evidence, investment, and communication • The ability to react to a crisis quickly (similar to wartime mobilisation)- however adaptation should also adopt a well-planned route • Adaptation implementation progressing, even with uncertainty involved, and addressing what's missing, rather than just listing actions already being done and focusing only on perfecting the knowledge of risks • Visible climate adaptation projects that have meaningful actions with outputs and outcomes rather than platitudes
Justice	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Addressing health and social inequalities that lead to climate vulnerability - in solutions as well as problems • Addressing inequalities and equal & fair actions that benefit all demographics • Considering just resilience
Resilience	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resilient and functioning communities and society • Considering long-term climate so that it is not just short-term resilience prioritised
Nature-Based Solutions & Green/Blue Infrastructure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Society values the importance of nature to adaptation i.e. natural flood prevention and focused on nature based solutions as a first preference • Promoting greenspace and green/blue infrastructure • Clustering countryside development and infrastructure rather than allowing sprawl • Adopting development that does not lock future generations into dependence on grey adaptive solutions • Recognising that there are multiple adaptation options (trees are not the only solution - marine, peatlands etc)
Visioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Focusing on behavioral change as well as technological or infrastructural changes, a shared vision for climate adaptation /climate futures • Forward thinking planning rather than 'next week' reactive planning • Considering future opportunities and challenges • Making places attractive for businesses to invest and encouraging growth
Resources/Funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strong sustained financial support to deliver action and multi-year budgets for ongoing projects • A financial analysis of the costs of action/inaction - the business case for adaptation is clear and routinely made (i.e. costs avoided/co benefits delivered underpin investment decisions) • Cost benefit assessments for actions driven by past or future projected impacts
Leadership/Champions and Co-ordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There are champions and agents of change - people who drive change because they believe in it - cool heads, warm hearts - these people are supported and valued • A nominated senior executive or political leader in place • Clear roles and responsibilities (especially in local authorities and public agencies) - and opportunities to discuss these as things change
Recognition of Emotion	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Safe - physically and emotionally • Climate change is seen as one of many stressors and addressed

Table 2: Summary of WS2 results: What steps did you take on your journey to shaping a well-adapted place?

Theme	Identified Activities
Education & Knowledge/Research and learning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developed the evidence-base by considering and then filling knowledge gaps • Carried out similar schemes before and/or learnt from what other people are doing - especially in 'safe' spaces where you don't need to be an 'expert' • Developed climate risk and opportunity assessments • Collaborated on research institute led projects and knowledge exchanges • Took part in awareness raising with elected officials and senior leaders to get political buy in • Highlighted the co-benefits of nature based solutions
Community Engagement, Communication and Collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Took part in co-creation initiatives and got different perspectives on what co-production means (evaluating co-production in research projects) • Worked through established governance mechanisms such as cross sector engagement to bring in a range of partners (e.g. not just local authorities) and engaged with senior management/elected officials to mainstream climate risk and adaptation into policies, designs, practices etc. • Established regional grouping of local authorities to share knowledge/ experience • Established local authority inter-departmental adaptation steering groups to carry forward adaptation planning and linked this back to regional groups to share learnings and resources • Developed site or community specific case studies (eg. Local campaigns) • Ran webinars and workshops for local authorities and the general public on nature-based solutions – with introductions and case studies relevant to departments/ communities • Encouraged well-connected staff to allow formal and informal engagement • Worked collaboratively with local partners including local authorities and community representatives to identify boundary spaces, tasks, people and opportunities - spanning sectors, silos and perspectives • Joined climate change community groups
Policy, Decision-Making and Planning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pushed for the establishment of adaptation legislation, policy and oversight bodies • Advocated for the inclusion of climate action (mitigation + adaptation) requirements into local authority community development policies • Advocated for regulatory and policy drivers that help and don't hinder adaptation • Promoted the theory of change • Advocated for and promoted guidelines/best practice in assessing risks, capacities, options
Monitoring, Evaluation and Accountability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advocated for schemes in place for monitoring and reporting on adaptation progress (eg. NI188) • Advocated for external reporting
Action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Worked with NGOs to establish nature-based solution projects e.g., InterReg • Promoted and supported the launch of the Forests for our future project • Encouraged Pilot Community Groups for Local Resilience Planning (coastal) - and linked this with academia
Visioning	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provided concrete examples of real life case studies to show what is possible and to inspire stakeholders • Co-Developed long term visions of climate resilience
Resources/Funding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Secured funding from government for adaptation partnerships for knowledge sharing and brokerage • Had funds in place for all aspects of adaptation before beginning • Developed a business case for action - looking at strategic, operational, economic, financial and management cases for setting up place-based adaptation initiatives • Secured additional staff resource to develop place based adaptation work • Employed capacity building and climate action training programmes for local authority staff –had the conditions in place for people to be able to use tools and resources • Secured clear and easy access to technical knowledge and adaptation tools (eg. Local Climate Impact Profile (LCLIP)) • Made links to local academic/research partners who have assisted on technical/evidence challenges
Leadership/Champions and Co-ordination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Advocated for leadership at national, regional, and local levels - local leadership and political commitment empowers action (e.g. climate emergency) • Had inspirational colleagues who championed adaptation actions

Table 3: Summary of WS2 Results: What capabilities are necessary to enable a well-adapted place?

Themes	Identified capabilities
Resources/Funding	Ability to access funding and resource (including convening and hosting capacity for outreach/research events)
	Ability to identify opportunities
	Technical and analytical skill
	Willingness and ability to undertake capacity evaluation and building
Leadership/Champions and Co-ordination	Leadership skills (Local and National)
	Enthusiasm and drive
	Ability to co-ordinate between stakeholders
	Organisational skills to set place based and specific goals
	Willingness to be accountable for actions
Policy, Decision-Making and Planning	Ability to obtain government support and legislation to drive policy
	Ability to align the coherence of policy and programmes with adaptation objectives
Visioning	Ability to envision a clear and compelling concept for sustainable development
Action	Ability to know when to take action
Mainstreaming & Holistic Approach	The ability to co-ordinate systems thinking/holistic approach/ mainstreaming
Community Engagement, Communication and Collaboration	Collaboration, engagement and empowerment skills
	Communication and listening skills to raise the public awareness of adaptation benefits
Education & Knowledge/Research	Ability to undertake/access research and a good evidence base
	Knowledge and understanding
Recognition of Emotion	Empathy to understand and address negative emotions associated with climate change
	Openness and Humility

Table 4: Summary of WS3 Results-Capability themes identified with prioritized capabilities indicated with an ‘*’

	Capability Themes
1	Legislation and Policy *
2	Leadership and Ownership *
3	Visioning
4	Justice
5	Flexibility, Practical Action and Delivery
6	Sustained and Secure funding and resource *
7	Mainstreaming and Holistic approach
8	Monitoring, Evaluation for success and learning and Accountability
9	Recognition of Emotion
10	Research, Knowledge and Expertise *
11	Facilitation skills and the characteristics of conveners
12	Community education, engagement, involvement and empowerment *
13	Collaboration, cross-sectoral networks and partnerships *

Table 5: Summary of WS4 Results-Maturity mapping of top 6 prioritised capabilities

Capability Theme	Less developed/mature	Medium developed/mature	More developed/mature
Legislation and Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Getting consultants in to do work for meeting minimum requirements—a tick box exercise Basic level of voluntary in house reporting on progress Capability of government to listen to experts and practitioners and policymakers is less developed Policymakers and practitioners rarely interact to devise policy - experience doesn't inform policy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Policy enables and supports regulation Adaptation reporting power begins to become employed in a mandatory rather than voluntary fashion Policy begins to recognise capacity building and progress through support mechanisms - capabilities are linked to each other and its recognised that you can't get far on one without the others Strategic coherence across policy begins Organisations/partnerships are undertaking action in house to address policy and build knowledge 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Very explicit adaptation outcomes -including future climate and not just current resilience Adaptation is constitutional - the government of day have to implement adaptation Mandatory legislation Independent regulators/ assessors The reporting on the specific scope of adaptation (capacity building and resource, communication, buy in) is in an uncomplicated format to enable ease of completion Reporting is integrated within existing structures rather than creating new ones (i.e., use KPIs rather than adaptation indicators) There are league tables comparing areas to each other/publicity Strategic coherence across policies and alignment between them
Collaboration, cross-sectoral networks and partnerships	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Key aims are identified Leaders and actors are unsure of key contacts – don't know who to speak to and where knowledge resides Adaptation is being carried out by multiple people alongside their other responsibilities rather than a dedicated person for co-ordinating work Diverse views and opinions are focused on their own narrow considerations rather than all adaptation actions (e.g. flood specialists only wanting to focus on flooding) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leaders know who to go to for specific knowledge and skills – actors are well known and involved Clear stipulation on what is required and expected from partners – recommend to have terms of reference to ensure what effort people need to input in each role There is a clear description of the entity's structure and aims 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring that provides legitimacy and transparency – and is trustworthy in order to understand the success of projects Sustained involvement from lead coordinators who recognise that partners come and go based on interest and external events and they need to be flexible enough to recognise and address this There is long term decision making, funding and resourcing and a dedicated, coordinated structure in pace for all partners Collaboration becomes the norm on adaptation –liaising with academics and NGO's prior to undertaking action to get a wide range of input
Research, Knowledge and Expertise	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is a general overview of climate risks – high level, tier 1, qualitative assessment The problem is described with evidence provided – There is a clear question to address. There are some links to academia 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A list of options and actions has been developed using evidence based research Officials have start moving from short term thinking to longer term thinking Adaptation is seen as a social and economic issue, not just an environmental issue and technical work informs conversations on it 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is access to technical experts - not ad hoc – there is a regular arrangement with technical and strategic experts who are an essential part of the core team working with government Information about climate risk is given appropriate weighting in the design process and this filters through to decision making
Sustained and Secure funding and resource	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Available funding sources are identified Funding for individual schemes rather than connected programmes is primarily used There is a disconnect between different strategies and different pots of money 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Target specific government initiatives that can apply to adaptation (i.e., make sure that adaptation is part of green recovery and its associated pot of money) Cost benefit analysis is heavily weighted on departmental objectives so by accounting for and promoting any for co-benefits (cross-department) there may be more available funding streams 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Different funding points and objectives are connected across scales –at a strategic level and for individual projects A range of cost options and a range of risk management options are provided to stakeholders to allow the best value solution Risks are taken to alter normal approaches to funding - there are uncertainties with nature based solutions but these are accepted if they are identified as the optimum solution

Leadership and Ownership	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Elected members influence political mandates on/for adaptation Leaders are supportive but not actually involved There is ownership within departments at the beginning and top down leadership driving starting actions There is an internal commitment made across the executive (government) to tackle Climate Change head on – with champions appointed by national government 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There is accountability at a middle management level There is national emphasis on adaptation There is political buy-in in terms of adaptation compared to mitigation (it may not be equal but adaptation is realised) Top down leadership is provided Bottom up ownership is provided 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Leaders convene steering groups and comes up with a plan of action – total involvement at a high level There are champions that are leaders and take ownership of the problem, driving action There is top level and officer level collaboration and engagement Leaders understand that it's not just about flood walls, or physical infrastructure but that there are multiple layers or involvement needed from basic education and engagement to mainstreaming of adaptation in all aspects of governance Individuals who have knowledge and enthusiasm to progress actions– someone to drive adaptation on a place-based scale
Community education, engagement, involvement and empowerment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Adaptation is purely a tick box exercise only carried out to meet requirements External workshops are held and the job considered done – there is no serious engagement at a place-based level The narrative is framed well to get initial local buy-in Building knowledge and understanding within communities has only started Government works with town and community councillors to raise awareness There is external evidence alongside the internal community viewpoint 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are workshops on raising awareness and how climate change affects specific areas Adaptation and mitigation are both included when addressing community groups in order to get more community buy-in There are neighbourhood led plans through a climate lenses There is action to build local capacity– not just employing an external consultant where you end up with a report but no community support 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There are community led plans for both mitigation and adaptation tailored to each 'place' There is random and fair selection for engagement – doesn't need to be targeted to garner interest There are citizens assemblies on adaptation issues – and the level of awareness raising and knowledge sharing necessary to hold these There is incentive for the people who need to be involved to get involved –the narrative is framed to engage and hold their interest There is a balanced perspective in order to get the actual view of the community (all citizens are engaged-not just those more willing to come forward)

Conclusions and Next Steps

With a focus on adaptation capabilities and how these enable the development of well-adapted places, this workshop demonstrated that these capabilities do not stand in isolation but are interconnected and build upon each other to drive and progress adaptation planning and implementation. The participants identified that many of the capabilities have crossovers and connections and have different approaches dependent upon the target audience. The participants highlighted that there is a huge amount of complexity involved in climate adaptation in the short-, medium- and long-term responses and that all stakeholders involved need to be fully engaged and committed. There also seemed to be consensus that while a 'big picture' vision is needed for successful adaptation it is at the small scale, granular, place-based level that there is stakeholder buy in and more successful adaptation practices.

We will use the capabilities and actions identified by the participants experience and expertise alongside our previous literature research of international best practice and ongoing literature review on adaptation capabilities (both can be provided upon request) as a basis to create a draft Capability Maturity Model (CMM) to inform subsequent workshops.

The TalX team would like to thank all the attendees for their active participation and willingness to share their insights and experience in order to promote and enable climate adaptation actions in Britain and Ireland.

Appendix 1: Participant list for the Workshop

Name	Country	Organisation
David Mellett	Ireland	Mayo County Council (Atlantic Seaboard North CARO)
Sean O'Leary	Ireland	Environmental Protection Agency
Cathy Burns	Northern Ireland	Derry City and Strabane District Council
John Barry	Northern Ireland	Queens University Belfast
James Convery	Northern Ireland	Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs
John Early	Northern Ireland	Department of Agriculture, Environment and Rural Affairs
Lesley Hinshelwood	Scotland	South Lanarkshire Council
Tara Murray	Scotland	Aberdeenshire Council
Alan Netherwood	Wales	Netherwood Sustainable Futures (Consultancy)
Clive Walmsley	Wales	Natural Resources Wales
Lorraine Hutt	England	Environment Agency
Kristen Guida	England	London Climate Change Partnership
Kate Lonsdale	England	University of Leeds
Matt Ellis	England	Environment Agency

Appendix 2: Workshop Agenda

TalX Workshop: Exploring Practitioner Perspectives on Well Adapting Places

Date: March 29th and 30th, 2021

Venue: Online-Microsoft Teams

Purpose: The 1st workshop of the TalX project (<https://talx.ie/>) will provide an opportunity to garner insights on what defines ‘good’ place-based climate adaptation, the enablers and barriers to achieving ‘good’ place-based adaptation and the key capabilities necessary to develop and enhance ‘good’ place-based adaptation. This workshop is being delivered online and in two parts held on March 29th and 30th 2021. Please note that workshop proceedings will be recorded for research purposes.

- **Part 1 (March 29th, 2021)** will focus on determining the key characteristics of a good place-based adaptation and the capabilities required to achieve good place-based adaptation;
- **Part 2 (March 30th, 2021)** aims to identifying how adaptation capabilities can be developed to support the delivery of ‘good’ place -based adaptation.

Useful Information:

- In advance of the workshop and to make the most efficient use of time available, participants are asked to view a video presentation providing an overview of the TalX project. The video presentation has been made available at available [here](#)
- To support workshop activities, the MIRO platform will be employed. You can find a short introductory video on how to use Miro [here](#)

Access to the Workshop:

The workshop will be held online and through Microsoft Teams, the following links can be used to access the workshop

- [Teams Link for Workshop 1, Part 1 \(29th\)](#)
- [Teams Link for Workshop 1, Part 2 \(30th\)](#)

Workshop Agenda:

Part 1 (Monday March 29th, 2021):

Time	Title	Presenter
14:00	Welcome and Introductions	Barry O'Dwyer (UCC)
14:15	Workshop Overview	Denise McCullagh (UCC)
14:25	Working Group Principles	Anna Beswick (SNIFFER)
14:35	Work Session 1: Defining Good Place Based Adaptation	Denise McCullagh (UCC)
15:10	Work Session 2: Identifying Adaptation Capabilities	Jade Berman (Climate NI)
15:55	Wrap up and Close	Denise McCullagh (UCC)

Part 2 (Tuesday March 30th, 2021):

Time	Title	Presenter
14:00	Presentation of Findings from Part 1	Denise McCullagh (UCC)
14:05	Work Session 3: Refining Adaptation Capabilities	Jade Berman (Climate NI)
14:50	Break	
14:55	Work Session 4: Maturity Mapping	Anna Beswick (SNIFFER)
15:55	Wrap up and Close	Denise McCullagh (UCC)